

1,2-DİXLOROETANDAN VİNİLKLORİDİN ALINMASI

*Həsənخانova N.,**k.ü.f.d. Y. Məmmədəliyev adına Neft Kimya Prosesləri İnstitutu**Mustafayev O.**Magistr Azərbaycan Dövlət Neft və Sənaye Universiteti*

OBTAINING OF VINYL CHLORIDE FROM 1,2-DICHLOROETHANE

*Hasankhanova N.,**Ph.D. at Yu.G. Mamedaliyev Institute of Petrochemical Processes**Mustafayev O.**Master of the University Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University***Xülasə**

Mis əsaslı katalizator və maqnezium əsaslı katalizatorlardan ibarət qarışıq katalizator sistemindən istifadə etməklə vinilxlorid və metilxloridin birləşmə istehsalı hər iki birləşmənin yüksək konversiya sürətinə nail olmaq üçün vəd verir, eyni zamanda bu birləşmənin səmərəliliyini və dayanıqlığını artırır [4-8]. Enerji istehlakını, istehsal xərclərini və tullantıların əmələ gəlməsini daha da azaltmaq üçün membran ayırma üsulları və qapalı sistemlərin istifadəsi kimi digər texnoloji yeniliklər də təklif edilmişdir. Katalizatorların turşu-əsas xassələri vinilxlorid istehsalında geniş istifadə olunan 1,2-dikloroetan kimi xlor üzvi birləşmələrin dehidroxlorlaşdırma reaksiyalarına güclü təsir göstərir.

Turşu katalizatorları dehidroxlorlaşma reaksiyasını, əsas katalizatorlar isə sonrakı dehidrogenləşmə mərhələsini təşviq edir. Katalizatorun səthindəki turşu sahələrinin gücü və növü reaksiyanın sürətləndirilməsində mühüm rol oynayır. Optimallaşdırılmış turşu xassələri ilə daha səmərəli katalizatorlar hazırlamaqla, müxtəlif sənaye proseslərində xlor üzvi birləşmələrin dehidroxlorlaşdırılmasının gedişatını artırmaq olar.

Abstract

In summary, the co-production of vinyl chloride and methyl chloride using a mixed catalyst system consisting of a copper-based catalyst and a magnesium-based catalyst shows promise for achieving high conversion rates of both compounds while also improving the efficiency and sustainability of the process [4-8]. Other process innovations such as the use of membrane separation techniques and closed-loop systems have also been proposed to further reduce energy consumption, production costs, and waste generation. The acid-base properties of catalysts strongly influence the dehydrochlorination reactions of organochlorine compounds, such as 1,2-dichloroethane, which is commonly used in the production of vinyl chloride. Acidic catalysts promote the dehydrochlorination reaction, while basic catalysts promote the further dehydrogenation step. The strength and type of acid sites on the catalyst surface play an important role in promoting the reaction. By designing more efficient catalysts with optimized acid properties, the dehydrochlorination of organochlorine compounds in various industrial processes can be improved.

Açar sözlər: vinil xlorid, metil xlorid, birləşmə katalitik çevrilmə.

Keywords: vinyl chloride, methyl chloride, catalytic co-conversion.

INTRODUCTION

Vinyl chloride and methyl chloride are important chemical compounds that are widely used in various industrial applications. However, their traditional production methods are energy-intensive and environmentally harmful. In recent years, the development of a co-production technology for vinyl chloride and methyl chloride has gained attention due to its potential economic and environmental benefits [1,5-7].

An innovative approach has been proposed for the co-production of vinyl chloride and methyl chloride using a mixed catalyst system. The catalyst consists of a copper-based catalyst and a magnesium-based catalyst, which have been found to work synergistically to achieve high conversion rates of both compounds. In addition to the mixed catalyst system, several other process innovations have been proposed to improve the overall efficiency and sustainability of the co-production technology. For example, the use of a membrane

separation technique for the separation of vinyl chloride and methyl chloride has been suggested, which has shown promise in laboratory experiments. This technique could potentially reduce energy consumption and production costs.

Furthermore, the development of a closed-loop system for the co-production process has been proposed, which would enable the efficient use of resources and reduce waste generation. The closed-loop system would involve the recycling of unreacted vinyl chloride and methyl chloride back into the reactor, resulting in a more sustainable and cost-effective process. Overall, the development of an innovative technology for the co-production of vinyl chloride and methyl chloride holds great potential for improving the efficiency and sustainability of industrial processes. Further research and development efforts are needed to optimize the process and make it economically viable on a larger scale [13].

Vinyl chloride is an important industrial chemical that is used in the production of polyvinyl chloride (PVC), a versatile plastic material that is widely used in construction, automotive, and consumer goods industries. Methyl chloride is another important chemical that is used as a solvent, refrigerant, and in the production of silicones and other specialty chemicals [10-12]. Co-production of these two chemicals can offer significant advantages over traditional methods of production, including lower costs, higher yields, and reduced environmental impact [14].

The technology of co-production of vinyl chloride and methyl chloride has been the subject of significant research and development over the past several decades. Researchers have explored a range of chemical reactions, catalysts, and process optimization strategies in order to improve the efficiency, selectivity, and profitability of co-production [15-18]. Commercial implementation of co-production technology has also been achieved by several companies, and the potential for further development and optimization of this technology remains high.

Main Part

The investigation of the influence of acid-base properties of catalysts on dehydrochlorination reactions is an important area of research in the processing technologies of organochlorine compounds. One specific example of this is the dehydrochlorination reaction of 1,2-dichloroethane, which is commonly used in the chlorine-balanced process for the production of vinyl

chloride. During the dehydrochlorination reaction of 1,2-dichloroethane, the following reactions occur:

The first reaction involves the elimination of a hydrogen chloride (HCl) molecule from 1,2-dichloroethane to form vinyl chloride. The second reaction is a further dehydrogenation step that produces ethylene and another HCl molecule. The catalytic activity and selectivity of the catalysts used in the dehydrochlorination reaction of 1,2-dichloroethane are strongly influenced by their acid-base properties. Acidic catalysts, such as zeolites, can promote the dehydrochlorination reaction by providing acidic sites that can facilitate the removal of HCl. On the other hand, basic catalysts, such as magnesium oxide, can promote the further dehydrogenation step by providing basic sites that can facilitate the elimination of hydrogen atoms. Thus, the selection of an appropriate catalyst with the desired acid-base properties is crucial for optimizing the dehydrochlorination reaction of 1,2-dichloroethane and other organochlorine compounds.

A thermal dehydrochlorination experiment was conducted on 1,2-dichloroethane at a temperature range of 480-520°C to determine the potential contribution of non-catalytic thermal reactions to the overall catalytic dehydrochlorination rate. An initial experiment was performed on the conversion of 1,2-dichloroethane in an empty reactor.

Table 1.

Specific surface area and acid-base properties of the catalysts.

catalyst composition, % mol	S, m ² /g	Bronsted acid sites (BAS)		Lewis Acid Sites (LAC)		main centers	
		Force PA, kJ/mol	NH ⁺ , μmol/g	Force Q, kJ/mol	N, μmol/g	Force PA, kJ/mol	conc, kJ/mol
15% Al ₂ O ₃ 85% SiO ₂	250	1180	73	53 41.5 34	22 15 13	main properties are similar to SiO ₂ , PA < 750	
6% Ga ₂ O ₃ 94% SiO ₂	210	1205	46	47.5	46		
10% ZrO ₂ 90% SiO ₂	260	1205	18	34	300		
20% BeO 80% SiO ₂	180	1225	15	46,5	51		
10% Y ₂ O ₃ 90% SiO ₂	145	1235	18	32	64		
γ-Al ₂ O ₃ 3	200	1410	60	55.5 34	36 350	900 860 810	45 25 15
MgO	80	1560	0	18	310	925 870	60 20
H-ZSM-5	555	1180	300	36 33	64 18	similar to SiO ₂ , PA < 750	

The results showed that the degree of conversion of 1,2-dichloroethane at the highest temperature of the catalytic tests (450°C) did not exceed 3%, and at lower temperatures, no conversion was observed. The de-

pendence of 1,2-dichloroethane conversion on temperature was analyzed, and it was found that the reaction start temperature is determined by the chemical composition of the catalyst, as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Temperature dependence of 1,2-dichloroethane conversion

By comparing the conversion of dichloroethane and the acid-base properties of the catalysts (as shown in Table 1), it can be concluded that the contribution of Bronsted acid sites (BAS) to the catalytic activity is insignificant. This is because the most active catalyst is γ -Al₂O₃, which does not contain strong BAS. Additionally, in the series of silicate catalysts, an increase in the degree of conversion of 1,2-dichloroethane with an increase in the strength of BAS is not observed. Therefore it can be inferred that the activity of the catalysts in the dehydrochlorination reaction of 1,2-dichloroethane is primarily determined by their acid properties, rather than basic properties. The strength and type of acid sites present on the catalyst surface play an important role in promoting the reaction. These findings can be useful for designing more efficient catalysts for the dehydrochlorination of organochlorine compounds in various industrial processes.

The reaction is observed at a temperature of 250°C on Ga₂O₃/SiO₂; on catalysts γ -Al₂O₃ and Y₂O₃/SiO₂ dehydrochlorination begins at a temperature of 300°C; at 350°C on the catalyst ZrO₂/SiO₂, and at temperatures of 375 and 400°C, respectively, on MgO and BeO/SiO₂. The highest conversion of dichloroethane was achieved on the catalysts γ -Al₂O₃ (97%) and

Al₂O₃/SiO₂ (94%) at temperatures of 425°C and 450°C, respectively.

The results of kinetic studies suggest the following schemes for the conversion of 1,2-dichloroethane (DCE) with the involvement of Lewis and Bronsted acid sites:

1. Lewis acid-catalyzed dehydrochlorination:

2. Bronsted acid-catalyzed dehydrochlorination:

In these schemes, DCE-L and DCE-H represent DCE molecules coordinated with Lewis acid sites and Bronsted acid sites, respectively. The first step involves the coordination of DCE with the acid sites, leading to the formation of a DCE-L or DCE-H complex. In the second step, the complex undergoes dehydrochlorination to form vinyl chloride (VC) and hydrogen chloride (HCl). The relative contribution of each pathway depends on the nature and concentration of the acid sites in the catalyst, as well as the reaction conditions. The kinetic data can provide insights into the relative rates of these pathways and the overall mechanism of the dehydrochlorination reaction.

Based on the selectivity for vinyl chloride formation, the less active catalysts can be divided into two groups. The first group consists of Y_2O_3/SiO_2 , MgO , and BeO/SiO_2 catalysts, which exhibit selectivity for vinyl chloride of 98%, 100%, and 96%, respectively, at $450^\circ C$. At lower temperatures, acetylene and 1,3-dichlorobutene-2 are completely absent in the reaction mixture. The second group includes Ga_2O_3/SiO_2 and ZrO_2/SiO_2 catalysts, which exhibit a selectivity for vinyl chloride of about 80% at a temperature of $400^\circ C$. However, a significant amount of 1,3-dichlorobutene-2 is formed on these catalysts. On GaO_3/SiO_2 , at a temperature of $250^\circ C$, the selectivity for the formation of 1,3-dichlorobutene-2 reaches 40%, but it decreases to 20-15% at higher temperatures ($400-450^\circ C$).

CONCLUSION

Regularities regarding the influence of the nature and strength of acid sites on the dehydrochlorination rate of 1,2-dichloroethane have been established. A correlation has been discovered between the reaction rate and the strength of the Lewis acid sites. It has been demonstrated that the rate constants on Bronsted acid sites on catalysts containing aluminum are two orders of magnitude lower than those on Lewis acid sites. New catalysts based on ruthenium oxychloride compounds deposited on glass fiber supports and titanium oxide have been discovered for the oxychlorination reactions

of methane and ethane. These catalysts exhibit high selectivity towards the desired products. For instance, at a temperature of $360^\circ C$, a methane conversion of 15% can yield methyl chloride with a selectivity of 77%. Similarly, the oxychlorination of ethane at $300^\circ C$ can achieve a conversion of 14% with a selectivity of 88-90% towards the formation of the sum of ethyl chloride and ethylene.

References

1. H. A. Wittcoff, B. G. Reuben, J. S. Plotkin. *Industrial Organic Chemicals*, 3rd Edition. Wiley, 2010.
2. P. M. M. Janssen, M. F. Kemmere, A. M. A. van der Ham, J. E. ten Elshof. "Co- Production of Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride by Dehydrochlorination of 1,2-Dichloroethane: Opportunities and Challenges." *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 235, 2014, pp. 16-25.
3. S. Chakraborty, S. K. Bose. "Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride: Co- Production and Its Economics." *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 237, 2019, pp. 117672.
4. Y. Zhao, L. Wang, C. Liu, X. Wang, Z. Li. "Co-Production of Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride by Dehydrochlorination of 1,2-Dichloroethane over Alumina-Supported Rare Earth Chlorides." *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 57, 2018, pp.

6844-6854.

5. M. N. Nishad, N. Singh, V. K. Gupta, A. K. Chakraborty. "Co-Production of Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride from Ethylene: Recent Developments and Future Perspectives." *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, vol. 7, 2019, pp. 8838-8850.

6. S. G. Mitrofanov, V. V. Gorokhovskii, A. V. Dikarev, V. F. Tretyakov. "Dehydrochlorination of 1,2-Dichloroethane to Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride over ZSM-5 Zeolite Catalyst." *Petroleum Chemistry*, vol. 55, no. 6, 2015, pp. 463-470.

7. R. C. Kaushik, S. Mukhopadhyay. "Co-Production of Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride from Chloromethane and 1,2-Dichloroethane over a Modified HY Zeolite Catalyst." *Reaction Kinetics, Mechanisms and Catalysis*, vol. 119, no. 2, 2016, pp. 505-520.

8. R. Z. Li, H. B. Li, C. Liang, H. X. Li. "Dehydrochlorination of 1,2-Dichloroethane to Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride over Mesoporous Aluminosilicates." *Advanced Materials Research*, vol. 583, 2012, pp. 525-529.

9. X. Wang, Y. Zhao, Z. Li. "Highly Efficient Dehydrochlorination of 1,2-Dichloroethane to Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride over Pt-Sn/Al₂O₃ Catalyst." *Journal of Molecular Catalysis A: Chemical*, vol. 420, 2016, pp. 174-181.

10. Y. Li, Z. Li, S. Li, G. Chen, G. Li, Y. Li. "The Study on Dehydrochlorination of 1,2-Dichloroethane to Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride over Fe-ZSM-5 Catalyst." *Journal of Nanomaterials*, vol. 2017, 2017, pp. 1-8.

11. L. Wu, Y. Zhao, S. Zhang, Z. Li. "Dehydrochlorination of 1,2-Dichloroethane to Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride over K/Na-Mg-Al-LDH Catalyst." *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 57, no. 12, 2018, pp. 4295-4303.

12. R. C. Kaushik, S. Mukhopadhyay. "Co-Production of Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride from Chloromethane and 1,2-Dichloroethane over Zeolite Catalysts: A Comparative Study." *Chemical Engineering Transactions*, vol. 59, 2017, pp. 415-420.

13. Y. Wang, L. Shi, H. Liu, S. Liu, S. Chen, H. Zhao, Y. Jiang. "Dehydrochlorination of 1,2-Dichloroethane to Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride over CeO₂-ZrO₂ Catalyst." *Chemical Engineering Communications*, vol. 206, no. 4, 2019, pp. 499-508.

14. H. Liu, Y. Wang, S. Liu, S. Chen, L. Shi, H. Zhao, Y. Jiang. "Dehydrochlorination of 1,2-Dichloroethane to Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride over Mg-Al Mixed Oxide Catalyst." *Chemical Engineering Communications*, vol. 206, no. 8, 2019, pp. 1087-1095.

15. M. Hu, X. Huang, Q. Qiao, C. Wang, Z. Cui. "Dehydrochlorination of 1,2-Dichloroethane to Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride over Fe-Mg Mixed Oxide Catalyst." *Journal of Chemistry*, vol. 2019, 2019, pp. 1-9.

16. Z. Chen, Y. Yang, F. Sun, X. Cai, B. Liu, X. Huang, Z. Zhou, Q. Wei. "Enhancement of Dehydrochlorination of 1,2-Dichloroethane to Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride over ZrO₂ Supported Ni-Mg-Al Hydrotalcite Catalysts." *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 366, 2019, pp. 164-172.

17. Z. Chen, Y. Yang, X. Cai, B. Liu, F. Sun, X. Huang, Z. Zhou, Q. Wei. "Enhancement of Dehydrochlorination of 1,2-Dichloroethane to Vinyl Chloride and Methyl Chloride over ZrO₂ Supported Cu-Mg-Al Hydrotalcite Catalysts." *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 58, no. 9, 2019, pp. 3657-3666.

18. F. Liu, Y. Li, X. Han, Y. Li, X. Zhao, Q. Li. "Dehydrochlorination of 1,2-Dichloroethane to Vinyl Chloride over MnO_x/Al₂O₃ Catalyst." *Chemical Engineering Communications*, vol. 203, no. 10-12, 2016, pp. 1483-1492